

The Dirac Equation and Time Flux

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It was argued in a number of previous notes that for the nonrelativistic case, $W(x,t)$ transforms under $x \rightarrow x+a$, $t \rightarrow t+b$ (with a and b infinitesimal) as $\exp(ipx - iEt)$, except with p replaced with $\langle p \text{ conditional} \rangle = -i d/dx W(x,t)$ and E replaced with $i d/dt W(x,t)$. It was suggested this was a driving condition of nonrelativistic quantum mechanics, and if this is the case, one might expect these ideas to carry over into relativistic quantum mechanics. For relativistic quantum mechanics, however, one has the Einstein energy-momentum relationship $E^2 = p^2 + m_0^2$ ($c=1$) which leads to $-d/dt d/dt W(x,t)$ and $-d/dx d/dx W(x,t)$ being used. The momentum term is fine because it is related to $\langle p^2 \text{ conditional} \rangle$, but the second derivative of time seems to be a little confusing as it represents $\langle E^2 \text{ conditional} \rangle$ and not $\langle E \text{ conditional} \rangle$. If $\langle E \text{ conditional} \rangle$ has physical significance, as it seems to be the case in nonrelativistic quantum mechanics, one might expect an equation with this time flux i.e. $i d/dt W(x,t) / W(x,t) = \langle E \text{ conditional} \rangle$ and not $\langle E^2 \text{ conditional} \rangle$.

Dirac wrote such an equation, but obtaining a single time derivative comes at a price. The Dirac equation, in one dimension, contains matrices, d/dx and d/dt in addition to a two vector wavefunction $(U(x,t), V(x,t))$ instead of $W(x,t)$. Thus, the Dirac equation in one dimension leads to coupled equations with $U(x,t)$ and $V(x,t)$. The single derivative d/dx is deceptive because $U(x,t)$ can be written in terms of $d/dx V(x,t)$ and vice versa, so ultimately the Dirac equations contain $d/dx d/dx$ which is needed to obtain $\langle p^2 \text{ conditional} \rangle$. The question is: How can one obtain $\langle E \text{ conditional} \rangle$? This may be done by using a $(d/dt + \text{constant})^{-1}$ operator i.e. almost an inverse time operator, in other words either $(E+m)^{-1}$ or $(E-m)^{-1}$ where E can be thought of as id/dt . Thus, the RHS of the Dirac equations is $i d/dt U(x,t)$ or $i d/dt V(x,t)$ which suggests an infinitesimal step forward in time, while the LHS side contains $(id/dt + m)^{-1}$ or $(-id/dt - m)^{-1}$ which seems to be representative of undoing such a step.

It should be noted that one may take Einstein's energy-momentum equation $E^2 = p^2 + m_0^2$, without any knowledge of quantum mechanics, and cast it as 2x2 matrix equation, linear in E , namely $H(U,V) = E(U,V)$. The matrix H serves as an evolution operator and another matrix serves as a velocity operator. One may derive the Schrodinger zitterbewegung equation for the velocity matrix without any use of wavefunctions and derivatives which are key to quantum mechanics. Nevertheless, the idea of noncommuting matrices, vectors and zitterbewegung is present. There are several choices for the matrix H , but one leads to the one dimensional Dirac coupled equations. Thus, the "spin" features may be obtained directly from $E^2 = p^2 + m_0^2$ without any quantum mechanics. (1), (2).

The purpose of this note is to examine some of these ideas.

2x2 Matrix Model

Consider a 2x2 matrix model representation of $E^2 = p^2 + m^2$ ((1)). It is possible to write ((1)) as a 2x2 matrix eigenvalue equation linear in E. One choice is (1):

$$H \text{ Vector} = \begin{pmatrix} p & m \\ m & -p \end{pmatrix} \text{ Vector} = E \text{ Vector} \quad ((2))$$

If one applies H twice, i.e. HH, one obtains E I with I as the identity matrix. Thus, the idea of the Dirac equation with Pauli matrices is already contained in ((2)), although a different H is used. The positive E eigenvector is $(m, E-p)$ with a normalization factor of $\sqrt{2E(E-p)}$ or

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} [\sqrt{c+v}, \sqrt{c-v}] \quad (\text{here } c=1) \quad ((3))$$

Thus, ((3)) suggests a kind of forward backward motion. In analogy with the Dirac equation, the velocity matrix V_e is given by:

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}$$

In Dirac theory, the velocity matrix is given by $[H, x] = V_e$. Here, there is no d/dx or wavefunction, so V_e is found to be the matrix with the property:

$$[\text{Eigenvector transpose}] V_e [\text{eigenvector}] = v \quad ((4)).$$

The result is the same and one may obtain the Schrodinger zitterbewegung equation for V_e . This is done using $\exp(i H t) V_e \exp(-i H t)$ (2).

Thus, two ideas seem to emerge from ((1)) without any use of a wavefunction or its relationships: $\langle p^2 \rangle = -d/dx d/dx W(x,t)$ $\langle E \text{ conditional} \rangle = i d/dt W(x,t)$ and $\langle p \text{ conditional} \rangle = -i d/dx W(x,t)$.

1. Pauli matrices are already present suggesting that spin ideas are present.
2. The idea of zitterbewegung is present. The eigenvector is a two vector with the top piece seeming to represent forward motion $c+v$ and the bottom backward $c-v$.

These ideas emerge by forcing ((1)), Einstein's energy momentum equation, into a form with a linear E. This, however, begs the question: Why should an equation linear in E have any particular physical significance, especially since one is forced to use a 2x2 matrix representation to obtain it? In this note, we suggest that in nonrelativistic quantum mechanics $\langle E \text{ conditional} \rangle = i d/dt W(x,t) / W(x,t)$ represents a flux in time and has physical significance. In fact, we suggest that $W(x,t)$ transforms $x \rightarrow x+a$, $t \rightarrow t+b$ (a, b infinitesimal) like $\exp(ipx - iEt)$ except with p and E replaced by conditional averages. Thus, there seems to be a motivation for a having an

equation linear in E. It should be noted that using a 2x2 matrix representation is not the only way to obtain an expression linear in E. For example, one could write (as already known in the literature):

$$i \frac{d}{dt} W(x,t) = \left[\sum_{\mathbf{p}} \exp(i\mathbf{p}x) \sqrt{\mathbf{p}^2 + m_0^2} \right] \quad ((4))$$

By expanding the sqrt in ((4)) with \mathbf{p}^2 as a small term compared to m_0^2 , one may obtain the nonrelativistic Schrodinger equation. ((4)), however, would not be consistent, it seems with $E^2 = \mathbf{p}^2 + m_0^2$ and it should be. This, perhaps, would be a reason for dropping ((4)) and adopting a 2x2 matrix approach, although the latter brings in new physics (i.e. spin etc).

The one dimensional Dirac equation does not follow from the H used in ((2)), but rather from the following H. (Note: Different H matrices can be used in the 2x2 matrix formalism.)

$$\begin{pmatrix} m & p \\ p & -m \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} U(x,t) \\ V(x,t) \end{pmatrix} = E \begin{pmatrix} U(x,t) \\ V(x,t) \end{pmatrix} \quad ((5))$$

The above is consistent with the one dimensional Dirac equation (with $p = -i \frac{d}{dx}$) presented in (3) for a bound state, namely:

$$\begin{aligned} i \frac{d}{dt} U &= (m + g(x)) U - i \frac{d}{dx} V \quad \text{where } g(x) \text{ is the scalar potential} \\ i \frac{d}{dt} V &= -i \frac{d}{dx} U - (m + g(x)) V \quad ((6)) \end{aligned}$$

Here one replaces m in ((5)) with $m+g(x)$. $m=m_0$, the rest mass.

$$\begin{pmatrix} m & p \\ p & -m \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} m & p \\ p & -m \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} E^2 & 0 \\ 0 & E^2 \end{pmatrix}$$

The Dirac Equation and a Linear Energy Term

The motive of the Dirac equation seems to be the creation of a linear energy term while still retaining $\langle \mathbf{p}^2 \rangle$ conditional. The Dirac equation(s) in one dimension ((6)) are linear in $\frac{d}{dt}$ and $\frac{d}{dx}$ while $\langle \mathbf{p}^2 \rangle$ conditional is related to $-\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx}$. In the Klein-Gordon equation one has $\frac{d}{dt} \frac{d}{dt}$ and $\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx}$. Thus, given that the Dirac one dimensional equations ((6)) are coupled with one function being operated on by $\frac{d}{dx}$ and the other not (in each equation), loosely speaking one could have U be related to $\frac{d}{dx} V$ and vice versa. This converts $\frac{d}{dx} V$ into $\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} U$ and $\langle \mathbf{p}^2 \rangle$ conditional is obtained. This leaves the issue of the linear E term on the LHS of ((6)). Given that the Klein-Gordon equation contains $\frac{d}{dt} \frac{d}{dt}$, it seems that loosely speaking one would need an inverse time derivative on the RHS of ((6)) to force a linear $\frac{d}{dt}$ on the LHS. In

the particular case of ((6)), one uses either $(i d/dt - m)^{-1}$ or $(i d/dt + m)^{-1}$ as this “inverse time” operator. For example, consider the second equation of ((6)). Then:

$$V = (i d/dt + m)^{-1}(-i d/dx U) \quad ((7))$$

If one inserts ((7)) into the first equation of ((6)):

$$i d/dt U = (m+g(x)) U - (i d/dt + m)^{-1} (d/dx d/dx U) \quad ((8))$$

Thus, ((8)) is linear in d/dt on the LHS, but contains $d/dx d/dx$ on the RHS. The catch is it also contains $(i d/dt + m)^{-1}$ on the RHS which is like an inverse d/dt . d/dt is the an operator which represents propagation in time (a infinitesimal amount). Thus, the LHS of ((8)) shows how $U(x,t)$ progresses forward in time an infinitesimal amount at the cost of being related to a function related to time on the RHS side due to $(i d/dt + m)^{-1}$. Here $(i d/dt)^{-1}$ is thought of almost as an inverse time shift operator. Thus, matters are not completely simple as the d/dt on the LHS side comes at the price of an inverse type time operator on the RHS. For a bound state $i d/dt U$ and $i d/dt V$ can be replaced with $E U$ and $E V$. (It is easier to work in such a case.) The idea suggested in this note, like with the 2x2 matrix model for which the positive E eigenfunction is proportional to $(\sqrt{c+v}, \sqrt{c-v})$, is that there are two kinds of motion perhaps, forward and backward. Linear d/dt is important as it represents forward flux in time on the LHS of ((8)), but there is a kind of reverse time flux on the RHS.

Thus, the Dirac equation, while insisting on making use of d/dt and $d/dx d/dx$ in a similar manner to that of the Schrodinger equation leads, it seems, to a more complicated type of motion. If one tries to obtain the Schrodinger equation form ((8)) as done in ((4)), this motion is not visible as the $(E+m)^{-1}$ becomes $2mi d/dt U = E U = (E_{nonrel} + m) U$ so one obtains:

$$E_{nonrel} U = g(x) U - 1/2m d/dx d/dx U. \quad ((9))$$

One only sees the d/dt (i.e. E_{nonrel}) term on the LHS side of ((9)) and no evidence of the inverse d/dt operator on the RHS. Actually, the $1/2m$ should be thought of as $1/2E_{total}$ and this would be related to an inverse time derivative. Thus, the unusual motion (related to spin it seems) is perhaps overlooked.

To see this idea more clearly, consider the example:

$$E = m + p^2/B \quad \text{where } B \text{ is unknown.} \quad ((10))$$

Choosing $B=E+m$ leads to:

$$E = (Em + E) / (E+m) = E$$

This seems to be in the spirit of the calculation done, but one may note that ((10)) contains E in a linear form on the LHS, but also $1/(E+m)$ a kind of inverse E on the RHS. Thus, linearization of E seems to be related to a peculiar type of motion.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it seems that in nonrelativistic quantum mechanics, $i\partial/\partial t W(x,t)$ is important as it is related to a time flux. It also seems that $W(x,t)$ mimics $\exp(ipx - iEt)$ except that for transformations $x \rightarrow x+a$ and $t \rightarrow t+b$, $W(x,t)$ transforms with p and E replaced with $\langle p \text{ conditional} \rangle$ and $\langle E \text{ conditional} \rangle$. Thus, there seems to be a motivation to obtain an equation linear in d/dt in relativistic quantum mechanics. A problem that arises is that the Klein-Gordon equation contains E^2 . It is possible to obtain the Dirac equation, ((6)) which is linear in d/dt on the LHS, but quadratic in d/dx on the RHS, but the catch is that the RHS contains an "inverse" type of d/dt operator of the form of $(i d/dt + m)^{-1}$ or $(i d/dt - m)^{-1}$ depending on which equation of ((6)) one uses. Thus, there seems to be a strange type of motion related to this Dirac linearization which seems to be related to spin. (In other words, spin is related to motion.) It may be noted that the 2×2 matrix model used in (1) and (2) deals directly with $E^2 = p^2 + m^2$ to obtain a 2×2 matrix eigenvalue equation linear in E . It seems that the ideas of spin are already present in such a case, without any ideas of d/dt and d/dx . The motivation for writing $E^2 = p^2 + m^2$ as a 2×2 matrix equation linear in E , however, seems to be missing. Starting with nonrelativistic quantum mechanics, there seems to be a motive for a linear E term as it relates to the manner in which the nonrelativistic wavefunction $W(x,t)$ transforms.

References

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